

Antigypsyism

as a particular form of **Racism**
and/or anti-Roma **Discrimination**
and its **Tackling/Combating**

Paul Isaac Hagouel

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Thessaloniki

COUNCIL OF EUROPE

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Roma Women Association

Roma and Travellers

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Esteemed Mr. **Thorsten Afflerbach**, Esteemed Mr. **Marcos Andrade**, and Esteemed Madame **Valérie Poppe** of the Council of Europe, Roma & Travellers Team

Esteemed Mrs. **Yiannoúla Mágga**, President of the Roma Women Association of Dendropotamos (Greece) entity of implementation of the Political School

Esteemed Mr. **George Tsiákalos**, National Coordinator of the [Roma Political School 2021 _ Greece](#) Program

Esteemed Students – Trainees,

Good Evening,

I feel obliged to thank warmly the Council of Europe for financing the School as well as for its [CoE] continuous trust in the implementing entity, the [Association of Roma Women of Dendropotamos](#).¹ I take this opportunity to thank the aforementioned Association via its President Mrs. Mágga for the honor of inviting me. It would be an omission if I did not thank in the person of Mr. Tsiákalos, esteemed friend George, him personally as well as all those that contributed to the skillful planning of the School given the special circumstances due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

The sterile presentation of Antigypsyism does not promote – foster the desideratum: It does neither minimize it nor suggests or proposes methods of tackling and combatting. Furthermore, how would it be

ⁱ The following is an English version of the lecture – paper – presentation given in Greek on Sunday, 12 September 2021, in Thessaloniki ([here](#)), at the [Roma Political School 2021](#) for Greece. The school is financed by the Council of Europe and runs in partnership with Association of Roma Women of Dendropotamos in Greece. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/roma-and-travellers/-/roma-political-school-2021-launched-in-greece-and-portugal>

possible to, maybe, use the very foundations of Antigypsyism (which, in essence, it is the unfamiliarity of and aversion–fear of the other) as the springboard, as the means to fight–weed out the causa causans of this scourge? Also, and maybe, (use them) as an advantage in the (political) competition – electoral campaign for public office or for proactive civic engagement?

Antigypsyism ^{2 3} or Discrimination ⁴ against the Roma or anti–Roma Racism ⁵ is a particular form – manifestation of Societal Racism. It is important to understand and tackle it because it was crucial in the implementation of the Genocide of the Roma ⁶ that took place during World War II. Unfortunately History has showed and proved to us that the distance separating discriminatory manifestations and prejudices towards a particular group, however “benign” might be labelled by the perpetrators, from genocide is extremely short.

The person on the receiving end of or the one who experiences the stigmatization and, as a consequence, the discriminatory (or hateful, or prejudicial) comportment – such as Antigypsyism, is not in need of definitions. Nevertheless, in order to confront it more broadly, within the societies, we need to define it for the benefit of the whole, for all.

Since it is a manifestation of Racism, it is for this reason that I quote a generally acceptable definition of Racism. The [Gate of the Greek Language](#) defines it very aptly and succinctly as the perception – conception of those who believe that their race is superior to others which nature has condemned them to inherited inferiority (thus we have racial discrimination). An extension is the current prevailing Societal Racism for similar perception and behavior to the detriment of social groups that are disadvantaged or different. I note that the word race originates from the Italian word *razza*.

For the **definition** of Antigypsyism I choose the non–legally binding working definition of the International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance ([IHRA](#)) of 2020. Below I quote the definition: ⁷

Antigypsyism/anti-Roma discrimination is a manifestation of individual expressions and acts as well as institutional policies and practices of marginalization, exclusion, physical violence, devaluation of Roma cultures and lifestyles, and hate speech directed at Roma as well as other individuals and groups perceived, stigmatized, or persecuted during the Nazi era, and still today, as

“Gypsies.” This leads to the treatment of Roma as an alleged alien group and associates them with a series of pejorative stereotypes and distorted images that represent a specific form of racism.

To guide the IHRA in its work, the following is being recognized:

Antigypsyism/anti-Roma discrimination has existed for centuries. It was an essential element in the persecution and annihilation policies against Roma as perpetrated by Nazi Germany, and those fascist and extreme nationalist partners and other collaborators who participated in these crimes.

Antigypsyism/anti-Roma discrimination did not start with or end after the Nazi era but continues to be a central element in crimes perpetrated against Roma. In spite of the important work done by the United Nations, the European Union, the Council of Europe, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, and other international bodies, the stereotypes and prejudices about Roma have not been delegitimized or discredited vigorously enough so that they continue to persist and can be deployed largely unchallenged.

Antigypsyism/anti-Roma discrimination is a multi-faceted phenomenon that has widespread social and political acceptance. It is a critical obstacle to the inclusion of Roma in broader society, and it acts to prevent Roma from enjoying equal rights, opportunities, and gainful social-economic participation.

Explanatory examples follow as well as modern manifestations of Antigypsyism [see the [Definition](#)]

The widespread Antigypsyism and anti Roma Racism played a pivotal role and was instrumental in all subsequent actions, in several European countries, that lead to and justified the Genocide of the Roma. It is thus our duty to study ways and methods in order to tackle head-on the phenomenon and to counter the ingrained inclination of persons to tend to prejudices which lead them to negative assumptions for the “other” that conclude with stigmatization and the ascription of stereotypes. The first foundational step was (and so remains) the adoption of the definition as a guide for further actions. It is in this direction that International Organizations such as Council of Europe via the Roma and Travellers

Team and via ADI-ROM [Anti-Discrimination Initiative – ROM], the European Commission, and IHRA engage actively.

One of the main ways to combat Antigypsyism at its root is education and instruction. It so happens that the current goal of the IHRA [Committee of the Genocide of the Roma](#) is to prepare teaching recommendation on the genocide of the Roma for secondary schools. The Committee was so tasked by a unanimous decision of all member states at the Plenary meeting. This is identical with the Council of Europe and of the European Commission recommendation to include the History of our Roma co-citizens in History textbooks along with the history of the Genocide. It is certain that it will raise awareness and will support the affirmation of the Roma as an inseparable part by the dominant societal community. I am proud that this is taking place during the current [Greek Presidency of IHRA](#).

Beyond IHRA, the aim and the goal of each society should be the elimination of bigotry and racism and of their manifestations in general, but also of Antigypsyism. The combating of the *causae causans* of Antigypsyism (and all racisms), and not only of the manifestations of, should be the sought out and desirable outcome – the *desideratum*. However, surprisingly, countless researches analyze the phenomena of racism, Antigypsyism, Antisemitism, Anti-Judaism, racial discriminations mainly in the United States of America, without advancing substantive solutions and essential ways and methods to confront any kind of manifestation and/or the *causae causans* of the above. The usual solutions professed might, maybe, cure the symptoms but do not heal the disease radically, they do not eradicate and destroy the cancer.

For example, we note the anti-racist policies which are based on ethics and morality. The invocation of morality effectively empowers the discrimination because it is addressed to the “racially powerful” – the dominant person or group – and asks of him to show empathy thus, indirectly but clearly, “legitimizes” the mental dipole powerful – powerless. The same holds true for the laws on Human Rights in various countries. They (the laws) impose the rules but they do not change ingrained and deep-rooted perceptions and prejudices from one day to the other. There is a need for perseverance, effort, work, ad hoc actions, time and, especially, education and learning.

It is interesting that the President of the United States of America [Dwight Eisenhower](#), in the wake of the landmark US Supreme Court decision in

Brown vs. Topeka Board of Education that declared segregation in public schools unconstitutional in 1954⁸, allegedly stated that *you cannot change the hearts and minds of people with laws.*⁹ (also [here](#))

On that, the Reverend Martin Luther King replied, in 1963, that we must go on to say that:¹⁰

While it may be true that morality cannot be legislated, behavior can be regulated.

It may be true that the law cannot change the heart but it can restrain the heartless.

It may be true that the law cannot make a man love me but it can keep him from lynching me and I think that is pretty important, also.

The conclusion is that legislation restricts somehow the manifestations but does not eradicate the *causae causans*.

It is imperative, through education and social practices, to prove that Racism and Antigypsyism harms the society as a whole and not only the recipient of the discriminatory behavior. It harms the racist himself.¹¹ When you marginalize one group, in our case of interest the Roma, then you impede their development, their education, their opportunity to work constructively and rewardingly for themselves but, also, for all the society. In the end they cannot take advantage of the same opportunities that are open to the mainstream population. The broader society will never get to know what contributions “misses”, potentially, in the arts, the sciences, the letters, the crafts and professions. The conscientious or/and the opportunistic racist misses opportunities of association and/or mutually beneficial transactions when he barricades himself or feels aversion. The selfish and, simultaneously, racist mindset of “*I am not a gypsy, what do I care what they have to go through?*” should be immediately discredited and shouldn’t be condoned silently. Just the opposite, the racist should care for all of the above as stated; Furthermore, he never knows, and cannot be excluded, that he might find himself in the situation the “gypsy” is now.

Diversity offers more opportunities for the advancement of the society as a whole and we should embrace. Otherwise, we are in danger mental consanguinity. Education is what weeds out stereotypes because it cannot adopt doctrines and unfounded beliefs as scientific truths. It has been proven that racism (the way it is understood here) has no scientific base

irrespective of all the attempts on many occasions and eras to prove otherwise [[1](#), [2](#), [3](#), & [video](#)]. Eugenics, that reached its apex before WWII and even in the first post war decades, has been fully discredited. Thus, de facto, someone cannot be considered rational and, simultaneously, profess racist ideas. This person is dangerous for all because he might consider any theory or doctrine as the real truth. And this goes beyond the subject person or group of his initial targeted biases and preconceptions.

How did we end up with Antigypsyism and/or anti–Roma racism and discriminations? Which are its anthropological origins, why it persists with pernicious consequences, what are the Greek Particularities;

Roma originated from the [Indian subcontinent](#) and they [dispersed](#) to the whole of Europe mainly from the Greek Geographic Region. We find them everywhere in the middle of the 16th century.¹² Then they were called (derogatorily) either Tsiganes, Zigeuner from the Greek–Byzantine Αθίγγανος [untouchable] or Gypsies from the word Egypt (since, falsely, some believed that they originated from Egypt). From the very beginning a different language, social customs and traditions and, in many instances, darker skin color differentiated them from the long–established ethnic groups of Europe. It is during the Middle Ages that the “invention” and the conceptualization of the race (from the Italian *razza*) was born.¹³ Thus, the discrimination that the Roma faced was racial due to skin color as well as social ostracism and marginalization due to preconceptions. The dominant population group ascribed biological inferiority in skin color which was accompanied by negative associative notions. Here, as it also holds true for African Americans, the (physical) difference is obvious, the skin color. So, based on color, provenance, alien–not mainstream culture and way of life they were stigmatized with stereotypes and generalizations. The stereotypes lead to preconceptions, and the preconceptions lead to discrimination and, in many instances, hate. The last lead even to their enslavement in Romania! (rob = slave _ see movie [Aferim!](#) [[reviews](#) here]).

Fast forward in history, the creation and establishment of nation–states burdened even more the status of the Roma in society. An additional hurdle surfaced, that of the inclusion of either a numeric minority or an ethnic minority into the arbitrarily defined national corpus. Ethnicity¹⁴ is an abstract notion whereas – juxtaposed to – the person, the civilian is not.

Roma, in the course of history, were negatively treated in almost all countries where they lived, in some worse than others if we are allowed to classify and quantify the maltreatment. The term accidentally pregnant cannot apply to discriminatory practices. The path to persecutions, deportations, concentrationary internments and, finally, genocide from the few and “mild” discriminatory manifestations and injustices looms today hopelessly short.

Some subfields of Anthropology such as biological anthropology, the linguistic and cultural anthropology, study the biological and cultural diversity but also the similarities between humans. Also, Anthropology teaches us that that pitting one group against another occurs in culture after culture and nation after nation. However, not even one gene has yet been found that causes this to happen and that it is the cause of this behavior.

Actually, what we mean by the word race in everyday parlance is, to a great degree, an arbitrary social mental construct. Racism emanates from a fallacious (but, in many instances, conscientious!) combination of biological facts with socially pernicious constructed (erroneously) ideas and perceptions.¹⁵ How are the second ones formulated and structured? The innate tendency towards bias in to be found in the human brain. Bias helps to detect and locate differences and to hypothesize, make assumptions and/or draw conclusions based on those. However, when bias is unfortunately used to make negative hypothesis based on factors such as skin color, gender and other obvious secondary differentiating details and characteristics, then the person driven by those gets involved with bigotry which, in its turn sustains and nourishes systems of inequality. In addition, the social milieu and the age-old entrenched stereotypes are impediments to the discardment of these conceptions and perpetuate the problem.¹⁶

Especially in Greek society one of the points that the definition of Antigypsyism, which states with emphasis that of the attribution and reproach to some others non-Roma of stereotypes and the resulting negative misconceptions from those, manifests itself rather often. Thus, in some instances in everyday parlance, we hear the double derogatory saying (towards others and towards the Roma themselves) “*You are gypsy*” where gypsy is used metaphorically and incorporates all negative stereotypes.

So, the entrenched negative conceptions for the Roma are what sustain Antigypsyism and/or discrimination against the Roma in Greece, albeit in a relatively small segment of the population. Thus, even though, based on the Constitutional mandates, all civilians in Greece are de jure fully integrated in the national corpus and identified as Greeks, nevertheless their full inclusion and acceptance by the dominant and majoritarian society has yet to be achieved de facto, as is also the case in other countries. As it was stated above, zeal and tenacity are needed in order to make people eject and erase from their minds the negative stereotypes that they still carry. All mass media can help by stopping to reproduce these stereotypes and stop stigmatizing Roma for being Roma, something that contributes to generalization by recycling the preconceptions.

The partial integration of Roma in Greece is due, first, in the tendency of the segregation of Roma in areas where they constitute the majority. We cannot call them Ghettos because they aren't. Nonetheless, the social separation of different groups does not promote mutual understanding and acceptance of one group from the other and vice versa. The Roma remain the "others" but for the Roma the non-Roma are, also, the "others" the Gatzes or Balamoi. The other for the other is an other – {this, taken to the extreme, means that the whole country is inhabited by others!} It is a chronic marginalization which hampers the inclusion.

The second, and most important, reason for incomplete inclusion and incorporation is the scourge of illiteracy and, fortunately nowadays, the ever-decreasing school absenteeism. Education and schooling of Roma children is what will elevate the status and it is a sine qua non condition for their better living as adults. There is a need though for the children to attend schools together with non-Roma children as classmates. It is only that way that the close encounter, interactive engagements and communication will bring children closer and the other will cease to be the other. It has been fully demonstrated that segregated schools do not lead to the discreditation of the undue aversion that some feel for the Roma and even consider it natural.

It should be emphasized that Greece never enacted racist laws for any group. Institutional racism is non-existent and never was.

In conclusion, the priority in combating Antigypsyism should be the eradication of the *causae causans* of this scourge. Legislation obviates mainly the occasional violent manifestations. Invoking morality and

ethics is relatively ineffective as means to modify behavior radically. The latest researches and attempts in combating Antigypsyism, or plain racism, with the juxtaposition of the arguments that all miss out and are harmed, possibly shows the path that should be pursued and procedures that should be engaged.

I believe that the most purposeful proposition for actions and proactive measures in order to tackle and combat Antigypsyism has two, equally important, components: Education, Schooling, Upbringing and State Policy.

Thus, for Education I would propose (non–exhaustive list):

Inclusion of the particularities of the History of the Roma Greeks in the curriculum of school history. Incorporation of their history in the national narrative. Antigypsyism thrives where there is ignorance and superstition.

Full comprehension that the Roma participate, fully and equally, in the Greek society.

Inclusion of the topic of the Genocide of the Roma in the History course [lesson].

A course [lesson] should be introduced in the schools where they will teach that Antigypsyism, and also any other racism, harms the society as a whole and not only the Roma fellow citizens. Our youth should be told how to start a conversation and, with logical arguments, engage and confront prejudiced or, simply, irrational persons. ¹⁷

Inclusion of a textbook chapter in the Biology lesson which would prove and thus, simultaneously, discredit and denigrate the undocumented so called scientific racism. (The teachers) should demonstrate that there exists no biological basis for Antigypsyism (or for any form of societal racism).

For the State I would propose (non–exhaustive list):

Dynamic actions and measures which would reinforce even more the incorporation into the wider society.

New courses in the History of the Roma in the Greek Universities, beyond the already established innovative [course](#) ¹⁸ at the [Aristotle University of Thessaloniki](#).

Safeguarding the historic Roma neighborhoods of particular character found in various cities as an integral part of our cultural patrimony,

Inclusion of the historic narrative of Roma Greeks with simultaneous exhibition (among others) of various artifacts and other objects in the Museums of the country, pertinent with the subject.

Last, but not least, I left for the end, first, the element of pride: All Roma and Romnija should be proud of their heritage, you should be proud of your particular cultural and historical heritage. This along with the second element that of that Antigypsyism might entail a little the factor of jealousy of the other towards you, maybe are some of your arrows in your quiver with which you will either seek public office or you will be proactive civic persons. Furthermore, those same characteristics will establish you, in the eyes and minds of the others, as capable of carrying through with the tasks of any position with which your fellow citizens might honor you.

I am optimistic.

I thank you very much and I wish you Success with the School.

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¹ All world wide web [www] URLs and hyperlinks were retrieved and valid on 10 September 2021 except otherwise noted

² Πωλ Ισαάκ Χάγουελ, *Αντιτσιγγανισμός / Ρατσισμός εναντίον των Ρομά: Ποράϊμος – Σαμουνταριπέν, Ο ορισμός της IHRA 2020, Ελληνικές Ιδιαιτερότητες*, 7 Νοεμβρίου 2020, Roma Political School II 2020, Συμβούλιο της Ευρώπης και Σύλλογος Γυναικών Ρομά Δενδροποτάμου, Θεσσαλονίκη _ {Paul Isaac Hagouel, *Antigypsyism / Racism against the Roma: Porajmos – Samudaripen, the 2020 IHRA definition, Greek Particularities*, 7 November 2020, Roma Political School II 2020, Council of Europe and Association of Roma Women of Dendropotamos, Thessaloniki (in Greek)}

³ *Antiziganismus, Gadge-Rassismus oder schlicht Rassismus? Die Diskussion um die Benennung der Diskriminierung und Ausgrenzung von Sinti und Roma*, von Britta Veltzke, Journalistin. Sintize, Sinti, Romnja und Roma werden ausgegrenzt und diskriminiert - doch wie sollte diese Form von Rassismus angemessen benannt werden? Die Debatte um den Begriff Antiziganismus. Produktion 11.02.2021, Spieldauer 00:33:54, hrsg. von Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung, Bonn (The Audio recording in German [here](#))

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- ⁵ Marion Demossier, David Lees, Aurélien Mondon and Nina Parish (Editors), *The Routledge Handbook of French Politics and Culture*, 2020, Routledge Taylor & Francis Group, 297 pages, New York. See Chapter: Marion Demossier, ***The new politics of racialisation in France: the Roma, territorialisation and mobility***, pp. 87-96
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- 6 Πωλ Ισαάκ Χάγουελ, *Η Γενοκτονία – το Ολοκαύτωμα – των Ρομά της Ευρώπης, Ποράϊμος – Φαράϊγιμος – Σαμουνταριπέν*, 25 Σεπτεμβρίου 2020, Roma Political School II 2020, Συμβούλιο της Ευρώπης και Σύλλογος Γυναικών Ρομά Δενδροποτάμου, Θεσσαλονίκη
Επίσης [εδώ](#) ο σύντομος χαιρετισμός μου στην [εκδήλωση μνήμης](#) της 2ας Αυγούστου 2021, στο Δενδροπόταμο, με πρωτοβουλία, πάλι, του Συλλόγου Γυναικών Ρομά Δενδροποτάμου.
{Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The Genocide – the Holocaust – of the Roma of Europe, Porajmos – Pharrajimos – Samudaripen*, 25 September 2020, Roma Political School II 2020, Council of Europe and Association of Roma Women of Dendropotamos, Thessaloniki (in Greek)
Also [here](#) is my brief salutation (in Greek) delivered during the [remembrance event](#) in honor of 2 August 2021, at Dendropotamos, again with the initiative of the Association of Roma Women}
- 7 I was a member of a core group [[pages 85–88 & picture page 87](#)] which wrote the final draft of the Definition of Antigypsyism which was, eventually, unanimously [adopted](#) by all member states of the IHRA on October 2020 during the German Presidency of the Alliance.
- 8 *Unanimous Decision by the Supreme Court of the United States of America in the case Brown versus Topeka Board of Education (State of Kansas) with which segregation of pupils in public schools based on skin color was judged unconstitutional.* From [The New York Times](#), 18 May 1954, the full [front](#) page and the full [decision](#) of the Court
- 9 Michael S. Mayer, *With Much Deliberation and Some Speed: Eisenhower and the Brown Decision*, Feb. 1986, [The Journal of Southern History](#), Vol. 52, No. 1, pp. 43-76, Southern Historical Association
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- 10 Justin Taylor, *Martin Luther King's Response to "You Can't Change the Heart through Legislation"*, DECEMBER 4, 2014, [The Gospel Coalition Deerfield Illinois](#)
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- 11 Heather McGhee, *The Sum of Us: What racism costs everyone and how we can prosper together*, 2021, One World imprint of Random House, 355 pages, Penguin Random House, New York and the article: *'Sum Of Us' Examines The Hidden Cost Of Racism — For Everyone*, book review
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